

Open Repositories Ireland: openAIRE v4 Metadata Guidance

For DSpace Repositories

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Introduction

The OpenAIRE Guidelines for Literature Repository Managers 4.0 are designed to help repository managers align their repositories with the latest OpenAIRE metadata standards. This document provides additional technical guidance for repository managers using DSpace to implement these guidelines and ensure that their systems meet OpenAIRE 4.0 requirements. It does not cover all OpenAIRE guidelines and is specific to v4.0. The advice focuses on DSpace – however, the guidelines are written in a generic way for all repositories. This guide focuses on providing guidance to the network of Ireland’s open access repositories, Open Repositories Ireland (ORI), when considering metadata.

Versions

Version	Authors	Notes
0.1	CL	First draft of document with data taken from analysis and discussions as part of pilot work of NORF OR project (Pilot group and Atmire): https://docs.google.com/spreadsheets/d/11OqoNw0_VwHka_b1h5FkodSkfwUueszOLITUQ5fytvDc/edit?gid=0#gid=0 . 22 Jan 2025
0.2	CJ	Review and reformat. 22 Jan 2025
0.3	CJ	Rework all metadata guidance to make them easier to understand and by providing examples from the repository and openAIRE side while also expand guidance notes. In addition, make sure guidance can be used by non DSpace users.
0.4	CJ	Changes after/during NORF OA Repos project board meeting 18 Feb 2025
1.0	CJ	Review and approval by PB. 27 Feb 2025.

Overview of OpenAIRE Guidelines 4.0

OpenAIRE 4.0 introduces a standardised way to expose research outputs by aligning metadata with international standards such as DataCite and CERIF. This facilitates the harvesting and aggregation of metadata for Open Access publications, ensuring compliance with European Commission policies and funder mandates. The following implementation guidance focuses on DSpace platform repositories and outlines the necessary steps to achieve compliance with OpenAIRE 4.0.

High level structure

The high level structure follows the field numbers and names from the OpenAIRE guidance https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/v4.0.0/application_profile.html

OpenAIRE field classifications

In the title of each section, it is mentioned to which extent a field is mandatory or not, according to the following OpenAIRE vocabulary.

Mandatory (M)

The property must always be present in the metadata. An empty value for the property is not allowed.

Mandatory if Applicable (MA)

When the property value can be obtained it must be present in the metadata

Recommended (R)

The use of the property is recommended

Optional (O)

It is not important whether the property is used or not, but if used it may provide complementary information about the resource

ORI aims to complete M and MA while strongly encouraging R.

Quickstart – Mapping Table

OpenAIRE target field	DSpace source field
1. Title (M)	dc.title
2. Creator (M)	dc.contributor.author
3. Contributor (MA)	dc.contributor.* excluding .author
4. Funding Reference (MA)	Linked entities or a single metadata field with SOLR authority,
5. Alternate Identifier (R)	dc.identifier.uri
6. Related Identifier (R)	dc.identifier.issn, dc.identifier.ismn, dc.identifier.govdoc, dc.identifier.isbn, dc.identifier.sici, dc.identifier.other, dc.identifier.doi
7. Embargo Period Date (MA)	dc.date.available => "Accepted" dc.date.embargo => "Available"
8. Language (MA)	dc.language.iso
9. Publisher (MA)	dc.publisher

10. Publication Date (M)	dc.date.issued => Issued dc.date.accepted => Accepted
11. Resource Type (M)	dc.type
12. Description (MA)	dc.description.abstract
13. Format (R)	DSpace automatically determines the format from the Bitstream format, not from item metadata.
14. Resource Identifier (M)	dc.identifier.uri
15. Access Rights (M)	dc.rights values but only when they end in "access" - otherwise ignored and crosswalked from bitstream information.
16. Source (R)	None currently
17. Subject (MA)	dc.subject
18. License Condition (M)	dc.rights* => license name dc.rights.uri* => license uri dc.date.issued as license condition start date
19. Coverage (R)	None currently
22. Resource Version (R)	oaire.version
23. File Location (MA)	Bitstream information (original bundle), the mimetype is crosswalked from the bitstream format,
24. Citation Title (R)	oaire.citation.title
25. Citation Volume (R)	oaire.citation.volume
26. Citation Issue (R)	oaire.citation.issue
27. Citation Start Page (R)	oaire.citation.startPage
28. Citation End Page (R)	oaire.citation.endPage
29. Citation Edition (R)	oaire.citation.edition
30. Citation Conference Place (R)	oaire.citation.conferencePlace

31. Citation Conference Date (R)	oire.citation.conferenceDate
----------------------------------	------------------------------

Metadata guidance

0. SAMPLE SECTION (M)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.boldfieldname
- **DSpace data example:** Title of Item
- **OpenAIRE XML output example:**

```
<datacite:titles>
  <datacite:title xml:lang="en_IE">Defining the Heathen Irish and the
  Pagan African: Two Similar Discourses a Century Apart</datacite:title
</datacite:titles>
```

- **Compliance status:** Compliant by default
- **Guidance:** No action required

1. Title (M)

[A name or title by which a resource is known.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.title
- **DSpace data example:** Defining the heathen Irish and the pagan African: two similar discourses a century apart
- **OpenAIRE XML output example**

```
<datacite:titles>
  <datacite:title xml:lang="en_IE">Defining the heathen Irish and the
  pagan African: two similar discourses a century apart</datacite:title>
</datacite:titles>
```

- **Compliance status:** Compliant by default
- **Guidance:** No action required

2. Creator (M)

[The authors of the publication in priority order. May be a corporate/institutional or personal name.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.contributor.author
- **DSpace data example:** Bateman, Fiona

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example (value example without linked ORCID) ##
<datacite:creators>
  <datacite:creator>
    <datacite:creatorName>Bateman, Fiona</datacite:creatorName>
  </datacite:creator>
</datacite:creators>
```

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example (value example with linked ORCID) ##
<datacite:creators>
  <datacite:creator>
    <datacite:creatorName>Bateman, Fiona</datacite:creatorName>
    <datacite:affiliation>University of Galway</datacite:affiliation>
    <datacite:nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID"
      schemeURI="http://orcid.org">1234-1234-1234-1234
    </datacite:nameIdentifier>
  </datacite:creator>
</datacite:creators>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Choose either to work with DSpace Person entities or with DSpace SOLR Authorities to ensure you can link an ORCID to the dc.contributor.author values, for all authors that have an ORCID.

3. Contributor (MA)

[The institution or person responsible for collecting, managing, distributing, or otherwise contributing to the development of the resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.contributor.* (excluding .author)
- **DSpace data example:**
 - dc.contributor.advisor = Ryder, Alan G
 - dc.contributor.funder = Taighde Éireann – Research Ireland

```
OpenAIRE XML output example with PIDs
<datacite:contributors>
  <datacite:contributor>
    <datacite:contributorName>Ryder, Alan G</datacite:contributorName>
    <datacite:nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ORCID"
      schemeURI="http://orcid.org">1234-1234-1234-1234
    </datacite:nameIdentifier>
  </datacite:contributor>
  <datacite:contributor>
    <datacite:contributorName>Taighde Éireann - Research
Ireland</datacite:contributorName>
    <datacite:nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
      schemeURI="http://ror.org">010t7sr36
    </datacite:nameIdentifier>
  </datacite:contributor>
</datacite:contributors>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Choose either to work with DSpace Person entities or with DSpace SOLR Authorities to ensure you can link an ORCID to the dc.contributor.* (excluding .author) values, for all authors that have an ORCID.
 - Ensure contributors (e.g., funders, supervisors, editors) are properly labelled.
 - Verify that all contributor metadata is suitable for public disclosure.

- Note that funder information stored in dc.contributor.funder will also be crosswalked.

4. Funding Reference (MA)

[Information about financial support \(funding\) for the resource being registered.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** Linked entities or a single metadata field with SOLR authority
- **DSpace data example:** Funder is “Research Ireland”, with funding stream named “Atmospheric Carbon Stream” and grant award is “decentralised web compute for carbon 2025”.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<oaire:fundingReferences>
  <oaire:fundingReference>
    <oaire:funderName>Research Ireland</datacite:funderName>
    <datacite:nameIdentifier nameIdentifierScheme="ROR"
      schemeURI="http://ror.org">010t7sr36
    </datacite:nameIdentifier>
    <oaire:fundingStream>Atmospheric Carbon Stream</oaire:fundingStream>
    <oaire:awardNumber
awardURI="http://research.ie"/>grants/acs/dwc/>643410</oaire:awardNumber>
    <oaire:awardTitle>Decentralised web compute for carbon
2025</oaire:awardTitle>
  </oaire:fundingReference>
</oaire:fundingReferences>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Implement authority control for funding references using OpenAIRE’s API to retrieve accurate funding data. Example data from openAIRE API <https://api.openaire.eu/search/projects?grantID=241196>.
 - Ensure funder identifiers and award numbers are included.
 - Use RORs for funder PIDs. Advice for this field will evolve as the community clarifies the approach to funder metadata.

5. Alternate Identifier (R)

An identifier or identifiers other than the primary Identifier applied to the resource being registered. This may be any alphanumeric string which is unique within its domain of issue. May be used for local identifiers. [AlternateIdentifier should be used for another identifier of the same instance \(same location, same file\).](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.identifier.uri
- **DSpace data example:** <https://doi.org/10.13025/29303>

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:identifier identifierType="DOI"> https://doi.org/10.13025/29303
</datacite:identifier>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance

- **Guidance:** If dc.identifier.uri contains more than one value, the other ones are exposed in “Alternate”. These can be handles, DOIs, ARKs etc.
 - Note the main identifier is in field “14. Resource Identifier” and for DSpace this is typically the handle.
 - If you chose to use dc.identifier.uri for DOIs it will be exposed here, if you chose dc.identifier.doi it will be exposed using “6. Related Identifier”.

6. Related Identifier (R)

An [identifier of a related resource](#) other than the primary Identifier applied to the resource being registered. You must also describe the relationship of the resource being registered and the related resource.

- **DSpace source field:** dc.identifier.issn, dc.identifier.ismn, dc.identifier.govdoc, dc.identifier.isbn, dc.identifier.sici, dc.identifier.other, dc.identifier.doi
- **DSpace data example:** dc.identifier.issn = 0029-3105

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:relatedIdentifier relatedIdentifierType="ISSN"
relationType="IsPartOf">0029-3105</datacite:relatedIdentifier>
</datacite:relatedIdentifiers>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Use to relate the item with other resources, the openAIRE guidelines has a list of controlled value. For example, “Describes”, “Cites”, “IsPartof”, “HasPart”. However, the DSpace openAIRE OAI-PMH crosswalk only applies “IsPartOf”, therefore only use related identifier in this context.
 - Note the wildcard (dc.identifier.*) does not work. Therefore dc.identifier.citation and dc.identifier.publisherdoi field do not get to crosswalked to openAIRE.
 - Example, DSpace:

<https://researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie/entities/publication/2d202871-2c08-4aad-8521-74199ebda342/full> and openAIRE OAI-PMH: https://researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie/server/oai/openaire4?verb=GetRecord&identifier=oai:researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie:10379/18509&metadataPrefix=oai_openaire.
 - Another example, showing multiple related identifiers, DSpace:

<https://researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie/entities/publication/8cced6f4-2a6f-4305-ba80-b2e8ecd80eaa/full> and openAIRE OAI-PMH: https://researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie/server/oai/openaire4?verb=GetRecord&identifier=oai:researchrepository.universityofgalway.ie:10379/16495&metadataPrefix=oai_openaire.

7. Embargo Period Date (MA)

[Dates relevant to describe an embargo period](#). A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource. Typically, Date will be associated with the creation or

availability of the resource. Recommended best practice for encoding the date value is defined in a profile of ISO 8601 [W3CDTF] and follows the YYYY-MM-DD format.

- **DSpace source field:** dc.date.available, dc.date.embargo
- **DSpace data example:** 2024-10-09

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:dates>
  <datacite:date dateType="Accepted">2024-10-01</datacite:date>
  <datacite:date dateType="Available">2024-12-01</datacite:date>
</datacite:dates>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** openAIRE spec uses DataCite Accepted to indicate the start of an embargo period and DataCite Available to indicate the end of an embargo period.
 - Ensure embargo end dates are recorded in dc.date.embargo, and use dc.date.issued to indicate the start of the embargo period (publication date).
 - Confirm that embargo dates are correctly mapped in metadata.

8. Language (MA)

[A language of the intellectual content of the resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.language.iso
- **DSpace data example:** eng

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<dc:language>eng</dc:language>
<dc:language>gle</dc:language>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** The DSpace openAIRE crosswalk converts some 2-letter ISO codes to the required three-letter ISO codes. For example, “en” in DSpace -> “eng” in openAIRE OAI-PMH. [Included transformations are found on the Github for DSpace.](#)
 - Irish isn’t included and there the source metadata should be updated to 3-letter codes and/or the crosswalk updated to include mapping adjustments to convert 2-letter ISO language codes to 3-letter codes (e.g., “ga” for Irish to “gle”).

9. Publisher (MA)

[An entity responsible for making the resource available. Examples of a Publisher include a person, an organisation, or a service. Typically, the name of a Publisher should be used to indicate the entity.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.publisher
- **DSpace data example:** eng

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<dc:publisher>
  University of Galway. Department of Computer Science
</dc:publisher>
<dc:publisher>John Wiley & Sons</dc:publisher>
```

- **Compliance status:** Compliant by default
- **Guidance:** No action required

10. Publication Date (M)

A date associated with an event in the life cycle of the resource. Typically, [associated with the creation or availability of the resource](#). Recommended best practice for encoding the date value is defined in a profile of ISO 8601 [W3CDTF] and follows the YYYY-MM-DD format.

- **DSpace source field:** dc.date.issued, dc.date.accepted
- **DSpace data example:** 2025-10-24

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:date dateType="Issued">2025-10-24</datacite:date>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Use dc.date.issued for the publication date. Year is mandatory, month and day are optional.
 - Optionally, dc.date.accepted should be used for the date when the publisher accepted the publication (but not to be used for anything else). Values for dc.date.accepted are not crosswalked out to OpenAIRE.

11. Resource Type (M)

[The type of scientific output the resource is a manifestation of. It describes the genre of the resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.type
- **DSpace data example:** journal article

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<oaire:resourceType resourceTypeGeneral="literature"
  uri="http://purl.org/coar/resource_type/c_6501">journal
  article</oaire:resourceType>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Align repository dc.type values with OpenAIRE's resource type vocabulary using term from [COAR Resource Type Vocabulary](#).
 - Evaluate the vocabulary configured in DSpace for dc.type and only offer those in your repository that you want people to use.
 - Note the resourceTypeGeneral attribute can be: literature, dataset, software, and other research product.

12. Description (MA)

[An account of the content of the resource](#). Description may include but is not limited to: an abstract, table of contents, reference to a graphical representation of content or a free-text account of the content.

- **DSpace source field:** dc.description.abstract
- **DSpace data example:** The primary source of uncertainty in radionuclide atmospheric transport and dispersion modelling is the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) schemes, highlighting the necessity for careful assessment and configuration of the PBL.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<dc:description>
  The primary source of uncertainty in radionuclide atmospheric transport and
  dispersion modelling is the Planetary Boundary Layer (PBL) schemes, highlighting
  the necessity for careful assessment and configuration of the PBL.
</dc:description>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Revise use of dc.description and dc.description.abstract, and do one of:
 - Recommended approach: all the values are in dc.description.abstract or
 - Extend the crosswalk to also map dc.description values out (in case there are important reasons why dc.description.abstract cannot be used.)
- dc.description.abstract should not contain markup (HTML, MathJax, Markdown, ...). However, UTF-8 symbols, including linebreaks, are allowed.
- Note Atmire Open Repository metadata profile offers a fallback mechanism that uses html.description.abstract, for including html on item pages. This way, dc.description.abstract can be kept clean of HTML or other markup.

13. Format (R)

[The physical or digital manifestation of the resource](#). Typically, Format may include the media-type or dimensions of the resource. Format may be used to determine the software, hardware or other equipment needed to display or operate the resource. Examples of dimensions include size and duration. Recommended best practice is to select a value from a controlled vocabulary (for example, the list of Internet Media Types [MIME] defining computer media formats).

- **DSpace source field:** DSpace automatically determines the format from the Bitstream format, not from item metadata.
- **DSpace data example:** PDF fulltext of a journal article.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<dc:format>application/pdf</dc:format>
<dc:format>application/xml</dc:format>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance

- **Guidance:** DSpace automatically determines the format from the Bitstream format, not from item metadata.
 - Do not confuse with Resource Type (M), type of academic output, or Resource Identifier (M), primary unique Identifier.

14. Resource Identifier (M)

[The Identifier is a unique string that identifies a resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.identifier.uri
- **DSpace data example:** PDF fulltext of a journal article.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:identifier
identifierType="Handle">http://hdl.handle.net/1234/5628</datacite:identifier>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** As an institution, ensure values in dc.identifier.uri can be considered as persistent URLs.
 - In DSpace, the first entry in dc.identifier.uri is typically the handle, acting as the default persistent identifier, though this may vary by system and supplier.
 - If you use handle.net, it means you trust in the persistence of handle.net.
 - If you use a value with an institutional domain, it means you take on responsibility of future resolving of the hostname (mergers with other institutions etc).
 - If dc.identifier.uri contains more than one value, the other ones are exposed in “Alternate”. These can be handles, DOIs, ARKs etc.
 - Handle vs DOI: Both are persistent identifiers, currently DataCite DOI services are more extensive.

15. Access Rights (M)

[Information about the right or mode the resource can be accessed.](#) If the metadata describe more than one resource, e.g. fulltext and supplementary material, the access right of the main resource should be provided.

- **DSpace source field:** dc.rights (if used) otherwise crosswalked from bitstream access policy information automatically. For example, the bitstream is accessible anonymously therefore it is open access).
- **DSpace data example:** dc.rights = open access or open access is determined by access policy on the item.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:rights rightsURI="http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2">open
access</datacite:rights>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance

- **Guidance:** Rely on the information getting crosswalked automatically from the bitstream access policy
 - the dc.rights field can be managed in the repository to include one of the openAIRE COAR Access Right Vocabulary terms (open access, embargoed access, restricted access, and metadata only access). The DSpace openAIRE crosswalk looks in the dc.rights field for values ending in *access and applies the correct mapping. If dc.rights does contain values ending in *access. DSpace determinee the access status based on the access policy of the item's bitstream (PDF). For example, When the bitstream is publicly accessible the 'open access' value is determined.
 - Typically, no action will be required, and the bitstream/PDF will be used
 - dc.rights can also be used for CC licences as the values don't end with *access
 - Make sure the one that you want to use to get rights information derived from, is marked as the "Primary" bitstream.

16. Source (R)

[A reference to a resource from which the present resource is derived.](#)

Best practice: Use only when the described resource is the result of digitisation of non-digital originals. Otherwise, 6. RelatedIdentifier (R). Optionally metadata about the current location and call number of the digitised publication can be added.

- **DSpace source field:** None currently
- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<dc:source>Ecology Letters (1461023X) Vol.4 (2001)</dc:source>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** [DSpace community plan to add a mapping](#) from dc.identifier.citation -> 16. Source (R)

17. Subject (MA)

[Subject, keyword, classification code, or key phrase describing the resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.subject
- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example
<datacite:subjects>
  <datacite:subject>Earth sciences and geology</datacite:subject>
  <datacite:subject subjectScheme="DDC" schemeURI="http://dewey.info/"
valueURI="">551 Geology, hydrology, meteorology
  </datacite:subject>
</datacite:subjects>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Free text subject values are allowed in DSpace.
 - OpenAIRE recommend the Dewey Decimal Classification (DDC) where no specific classification scheme is used.
 - DSpace provides the option to configure simple and hierarchical lists for selecting values from predefined vocabularies.
 - Using configured vocabularies reduces the likelihood of human error.
 - Where possible, it is recommended to configure selection lists for content types or collections that align with relevant standard vocabularies.

18. License Condition (M)

[Information about license rights held in and over the resource.](#)

- **DSpace source field:** dc.rights, dc.rights.uri, dc.date.issued
- **DSpace data example:** Licence is “Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial” <http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/> and the date issued is 2019-02-01.

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example

<oaire:licenseCondition startDate="2019-02-01"
uri="http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by-nc/4.0/">Creative Commons Attribution-
NonCommercial</oaire:licenseCondition>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:**
 - Even though this is marked as Recommended by OpenAIRE, it should be treated as Mandatory.
 - Use DSpace's Creative Commons license feature to manage licenses. Ensure dc.date.issued reflects the license start date.

19. Coverage (R)

[The extent or scope of the content of the resource.](#) Coverage will typically include temporal period (a period label, date, or date range) or jurisdiction (such as a named administrative entity).

- **DSpace source field:** None currently
- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example

<dc:coverage>2000-2010</dc:coverage>
<dc:coverage>scheme=historic; content=Ming Dynasty</dc:coverage>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** [DSpace community plan to add a mapping](#) and suggest dc.coverage.spatial & dc.coverage.temporal -> 19. Coverage (R)

22. Resource Version (R)

Depending on the resource type this property is used to indicate 1) the version number of a dataset or software or 2) the status in the publication process of journal articles.

- **DSpace source field:** oaire.version
- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example

<oaire:version>1.0.3</oaire:version>
<oaire:version
uri="http://purl.org/coar/version/c_be7fb7dd8ff6fe43">AM</oaire:version>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** No explicit code for this in the crosswalk, but this could be explained by the hypothesis that everything in the oaire schema is just crosswalked as-is without other explicit instructions.
 - Recommendation to adopt the [COAR vocabulary for resource versions](#). For example, AM = Accepted Manuscript etc.

23. File Location (MA)

[An unambiguous reference to the files](#), e.g. fulltext, the resource is associated with.

Repeat the property for each associated file.

- **DSpace source field:** Bitstream information (original bundle), the mimetype is crosswalked from the bitstream format
- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example

<oaire:file accessRightsURI="http://purl.org/coar/access_right/c_abf2"
mimeType="application/pdf" objectType="fulltext">http://link-to-the-
fulltext.org </oaire:file>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** Ensure bitstream MIME types are crosswalked from the original bundle. See GitHub #L877-L945 for technical guidance.

24 - 31. Citation Fields

Including

- 24. Citation Title (R), 25. Citation Volume (R), 26. Citation Issue (R), 27. Citation Start Page (R), 28. Citation End Page (R), 29. Citation Edition (R), 30. Citation Conference Place (R), 31. Citation Conference Date (R)
- **DSpace source fields:** oaire.citation.title, oaire.citation.volume, oaire.citation.issue, oaire.citation.startPage, oaire.citation.endPage, oaire.citation.edition, oaire.citation.conferencePlace, oaire.citation.conferenceDate

- **DSpace data example:**

```
## OpenAIRE XML output example for 24. Citation Title (R)  
<oaire:citationTitle>some Journal Title</oaire:citationTitle>
```

- **Compliance status:** Requires guidance
- **Guidance:** These fields introduced as part of the openaire default functionality in DSpace 7 and did not exist in earlier versions of DSpace.
 - If you are using another field for this same purpose, your oai crosswalk needs to be updated to get this field exposed to OpenAIRE.